

THE IMPORTANCE OF LEGAL AWARENESS AND LEGAL CULTURE IN LEGAL EDUCATION AND EDUCATION

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Abstract. This article analyzes the importance of legal upbringing and education in the development of legal consciousness and legal culture in society. Also, some solutions to this issue are given.

Keywords. Systematic and organic education, legal awareness, personal and community interests, legal education, education and training, discipline, legal promotion, norms of etiquette, civil servants, lawyers, management bodies, state symbols, state bodies.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПРАВОВОГО ОСОЗНАНИЯ И ПРАВОВОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ В ПРАВОВОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

Аннотация. В статье анализируется значение правового воспитания и образования в развитии правового сознания и правовой культуры в обществе. Также приведены некоторые решения данного вопроса.

Ключевые слова: Систематическое и органическое образование, правосознание, личные и общественные интересы, юридическое образование, воспитание и обучение, дисциплина, правовое продвижение, нормы этикета, государственные служащие, юристы, органы управления, государственные символы, государственные органы.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "No matter how perfect laws we create, no matter what reforms we carry out, if the legal knowledge, consciousness and culture of our citizens are not sufficient, it is difficult to achieve the expected results", "Respect for the Constitution and laws, legal consciousness and culture is the responsibility of every citizen, every official." it should become a way of life and activity of the individual", he said, life itself shows how important the legal reforms implemented in our country in recent years are for the development of the society.

Also, based on the Decree of the President of our country "On Fundamental Improvement of the System of Raising Legal Awareness and Legal Culture in Society", the "Concept of Raising Legal Culture in Society" was approved. The following issues were raised in it:

1) paying special attention to legal awareness and legal culture in society, first of all, systematic and organic education, instilling legal awareness and legal culture in all strata of the population, promoting the ideas of maintaining a balance between personal and community interests;

2) to deeply inculcate the concepts of rights and duties, honesty and purity, manners into the minds of the young generation, to teach the important aspects of our basic dictionary from childhood;

3) to organize legal-educational activities for the formation of legal culture among the population in harmony with the teaching of the history, religion, and national values of our people,

as well as to increase the sense of belonging to the country and patriotism by forming in every citizen a sense of pride in state symbols;

4) education and upbringing system, all institutions related to spirituality and enlightenment, to establish pure moral and high spiritual values in their activities and inculcate in public consciousness, and most importantly, to further increase the activity of citizens in all spheres of public life, in particular, within the framework of legal issues.

Improving the legal culture of young people starts not only in educational institutions, but also in the family. Law has a special place in the system of social sciences. Legal knowledge teaches how to take the right direction in different specific situations in life, to find the border between permitted and prohibited things, to choose legal ways and means of protecting one's rights and interests.

Legal knowledge expands the political level, helps the formation of beliefs, correct understanding of legal phenomena in life, conscious compliance with legal requirements, and active struggle for compliance with legal norms of all citizens.

Forms of legal education can be as follows:

- a) legal knowledge;
- b) legal campaign;
- c) works carried out by the public;
- g) getting to know the work of state bodies that protect the right (participation in investigations, court proceedings);
- d) participation in the meetings of recommending people's deputies for candidacy, in the work of juvenile commissions under local authorities.

Legal training can be carried out in a team or individually. Meetings with employees of state bodies protecting rights, organization of question-and-answer evenings, or formation of lawyers' associations will give positive results in attracting young people to legal knowledge and legal education. It is advisable to recommend special literature to a person in individual legal education and legal education, to arouse interest in him, to study the mental state of the student, and to conduct a conversation in a way that he can accept and understand.

Lawyers generally divide legal education methods into two types: persuasion and coercion.

The method of legal education is a set of several specific ways and methods, based on which people's minds and worldviews are affected. As a result of this, a sense of respect for the law is awakened in the students and it is ensured that the law is not violated. The most basic method is the method of persuasion. If a positive result is not achieved through persuasion, the method of coercion is used. It is also possible to use these two methods together in legal education.

Another of the scientific principles of legal education is to explain the reasons for the origin of the studied law or decision, and the objective necessity for it. If the student understands the general basis of the creation and adoption of laws, decisions and regulations, especially if he knows the reason for the adoption of the currently studied legal norm, he will consciously approach its implementation, and he will feel the need for the legal norm.

Comprehensive approach to education. An all-round approach to education is defined as determining the factors that contribute to the formation of the purpose of education in the mind of a person, relying on them in the forms and methods of education. Successful implementation of

these tasks depends on the mutual cooperation of the teacher and the students. The exchange of opinions of both parties, the clarification of legal concepts, and the determination of their life situation on the basis of unanimity will make a relevant change in the legal consciousness of the listeners and enrich it. For example, the educator wants to introduce the audience to the changes made to the labor law. The goal is to educate them to work in accordance with the changes in the law in labor relations, reflecting the content of the single law. For this, the educator should approach the issue broadly, show the reasons for the change in the law with the help of evidence, prove the essence of the new law, teach the procedure for its implementation, and explain the intended purpose with the help of examples.

The goal of educating a fully mature person requires that all directions of general education be carried out in harmony with each other. It is the duty of not one person, but the whole team. Legal education is also not for one person, because one educator is not able to know all the factors for the comprehensive formation of a person. A pedagogue can form only one or several directions of legal education in the mind of a person. In order to have a broad approach to legal education on a specific issue, a teacher should select factors related to this issue, gather them into a single topic, and harmonize them with the help of examples.

For example, the teacher-student should choose what laws should be studied in the education of the student's duty of loyalty to the citizens of Uzbekistan, find examples that apply to citizens, determine the measures to be taken by the state and society in case of violation of the civic duty, collect legal evidence, then it is necessary to develop broad topics of education and work on this topic. But it should not be forgotten that legal factors alone are not enough to form even a direction of legal consciousness.

Relying on the above analytical points, it is possible to put forward the following recommendations in order to improve the effectiveness of legal education in educational institutions:

1. Development of scientific-methodical recommendations on increasing the effectiveness of legal education, taking into account the specialty characteristics of educational institutions;
2. Dissemination of best practices in the field of legal education in the entire educational system, conducting mobile seminars and trainings in this field at the level of the republic, region, city, district and regions;
3. To achieve regular publication of scientific-methodical approaches, recommendations, didactic materials aimed at increasing the effectiveness of legal education in scientific journals in the Republic;
4. When forming and improving legal education, the family, community, and mass media should take a responsible view of their tasks in the field of education.

In conclusion, it can be said that lectures and conversations about law remain the main form of legal propaganda. Of course, the episodic nature of one-time events, thematic disconnection, has its negative aspects. It is not without reason that series of lectures and talks held in an organized manner, on a planned basis, series of topics, in contrast to one-time lectures, provide minors with a set of knowledge in a specific system, skills in the practical application of legal norms. Inculcates, can be carried out in harmony with curricula and school programs. At the same time, some conversations and lectures are considered to be the most important form of

reacting to legal events, promoting new laws, and meeting emerging needs. Meetings with practitioners of the court, prosecutor's office, and judicial bodies are extremely important. They always arouse interest in teenagers and cause discussion of legal issues.

Before such meetings, jurists get acquainted with the disciplinary situation in schools, vocational and technical educational institutions, youth groups, analyze the existing shortcomings and violations of the legal order, and provide information about the measures taken against offenders. Such meetings are held in the style of a "round table", free discussion and discussion.

But they require thorough preparation from lecturers and organizers. Thematic evenings, question and answer evenings organized for schools and educational institutions are also an effective form of promoting legal knowledge, and cultural palaces, cinemas, libraries, culture and recreation parks are used to hold them. Experience shows that such parties are more interesting in places where teenagers themselves actively participate in their preparation.

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